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Business, Economics & Management

- *Accounting & Taxation*
- *Business, Economics & Management (general)*
- *Development Economics*
- *Economic History*
- *Economic Policy*
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- *Educational Administration*
- *Emergency Management*
- *Entrepreneurship & Innovation*
- *Finance*
- *Game Theory and Decision Science*
- *Human Resources & Organizations*
- *International Business*
- *Marketing*
- *Strategic Management*
- *Tourism & Hospitality*

MARKETING ACTIVITY IN SPORTS ORGANIZATIONS

Iskakov Taiyrzhan Bahytbaevich

PhD, Acting Associate Professor, Kazakh Academy of Sports and Tourism, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Today, one of the most important components of the effective functioning of the sphere of physical culture and sports is marketing. The main prerequisites for the emergence and approval of marketing in this area are:

- revision of the prevailing paradigms: recognition of physical culture and sports as a service sector and a commodity form of a product of pedagogical work, reorientation of the physical culture movement from fulfilling the “planned” indicators set from above to the maximum possible satisfaction of the interests, requests and needs of the population;
- acquisition by physical culture and sports organizations of great autonomy, independence and freedom of activity, legal recognition of the equality of various types and forms of ownership;
- aggravation of competition between sports organizations, their desire to expand the sale of their services and obtain economic benefits.

The need for the development and practical application of marketing is recognized at all levels of organization and management of the physical culture movement - from the heads of sports organizations and their structural divisions to the federal level.

Being an integral part of the “Health, physical culture and social security” industry, physical culture and sports function in the market mode as a service sector, the main product of which (and, therefore, the leading object of marketing) are physical culture and sports services - organized forms of physical exercise and types of sports with various purposes, as well as activities that provide them (maintenance of a network of sports facilities, organization of services for their visitors during classes, trade, rental and repair of sports equipment and inventory, sports insurance services, etc.) [1].

The main subjects of marketing relations in physical culture and sports as a service sector are those involved in physical exercises and sports as the final consumers of physical culture and sports services; indirect consumers - enterprises, organizations, institutions that purchase the mentioned services for use in their activities; physical culture and sports organizations as producers of physical culture and sports services; the state represented by state bodies for physical culture and sports; marketing specialists - individuals, firms, divisions (departments, services, groups, etc.) of sports organizations specializing in specific marketing functions.

The content of marketing activities in the field of physical culture and sports can be characterized by answering the following traditional marketing questions: «Which client to focus on, who will make up the contingent of consumers? What services to produce and offer on the market? What quality? How much? Who will provide them? Where? When? At what price and under what conditions? ».

Adapting these questions to the field of physical culture and sports, we can distinguish the following main areas of marketing activity:

- determination of qualitative and price parameters of demand, characteristics and priorities in relation to potential and real consumers;
- formation of the range of services provided (by types of basic (physical culture and sports), related and additional services);
- assessment and provision of the required level of quality and competitiveness (demand) of the services provided;

- choice of pedagogical technologies (programs, methods, forms, means, methods, teaching and training methods, including methods and forms of control and evaluation, etc.) implemented as part of the provision of physical culture and sports services;

- selection and decision-making regarding the required volume (including duration) and mode (beginning of provision, degree of regularity, schedule) for the provision of services;

- selection and decision-making regarding the material and technical support for the provision of services (first of all, the choice of the type and category of physical culture and sports facilities, the level of material and technical equipment of the sports base in accordance with the requirements of the chosen pedagogical process and the needs of consumer groups);

Establish characteristics and priorities for personnel providing basic, additional and related services in the field of physical culture and sports:

- formation of prices for services, determination of conditions and forms of payment, ways of adapting prices;

- organization of promotion and sales of physical culture and sports services (selection of intermediaries, methods of sale and its stimulation);

- formation of a communication policy: design and organization of advertising activities (selection of addressees, media, distribution channels, content, forms and modes of submission of messages), organization of favorable public opinion, personal contacts (personal, telephone), etc.

Thus, the content of marketing activities in the field of physical culture and sports is connected, on the one hand, with the solution of classical marketing issues in relation to production, personnel, pricing, marketing and communication policies, on the other hand, it has a number of features. The most significant of them are the following: the predominantly non-commercial nature of market activities in the field of physical culture and sports, which is financed not so much by consumers, but by attracting funds from the state budget, various foundations, sponsors, patrons, etc. In physical culture and sports organizations, income from the sale of season tickets usually does not exceed 15% of the budget, the rest is state subsidies, funds from public organizations, sponsors, etc. In addition, it is non-profit sports organizations (children's and youth physical training clubs, children's and youth sports and sports and technical schools, specialized children's and youth sports and sports and technical schools of the Olympic reserve, schools of higher sportsmanship, voluntary physical culture and sports societies, physical culture and sports associations, sports clubs and leagues of amateur and professional sports, sports (physical culture and sports, sports and recreation) facilities, complexes and centers, Olympic training centers, etc.) dominate the industry [2].

Marketing in the field of physical culture and sports is part of an objective reality, an integral part of the life of modern society, its necessity and effectiveness are due to the current level of development of market relations, physical culture movement and the current socio-cultural traditions of society.

Marketing can be used both at the level of individual physical culture and sports organizations and their structural divisions, and at the regional and state levels.

Marketing is a multifaceted concept; according to its broad understanding, marketing in the field of physical culture and sports can be defined as a market-oriented system for managing physical culture movement.

In this capacity, it is aimed at identifying, forming, building up and most fully satisfying the current and future sports interests and needs of the population through the design, optimization and implementation of targeted programs at the federal, regional and local levels, implemented in the form of physical culture and sports services, as well as on so

that each employee of sports organizations and a representative of physical culture and sports management bodies thinks in terms of “consumer”, “need”, “market”.

Marketing is also a management concept, since it contains the logic of consistent implementation of the main management functions: analysis of the external and internal environment of a physical culture and sports organization, including awareness of the interests and needs of real and potential customers, society and the organization itself, programming of market and physical culture and sports activities, their implementation, monitoring of implementation, evaluation of both the activities themselves and their results. All this allows us to define marketing as a type of social management of demand, supply and implementation of physical culture and sports services, primarily in the interests of consumers, as well as sports organizations, the state and society as a whole [3].

In its modern understanding and content, marketing in the field of physical culture and sports is a very powerful and well-integrated technology of socio-cultural innovations. This is due to the fact that marketing begins and ends with the analysis of the general and physical culture of society and the individual. Moreover, starting from the study of lifestyle, marketing "at the end" of the implementation of the program forms a certain (first of all - a healthy, physically active) lifestyle. Thus, marketing appears to be an effective factor in the formation of the physical culture of society and the individual. The main task of marketing is, without encroaching on the sovereignty of the consumer, to shape his purchasing behavior in such a way that he becomes a permanent, lifelong supporter of services in the field of physical culture and sports, and at the same time prefers the services of the physical culture and sports organization that most effectively uses marketing and its capabilities.

Marketing in the field of physical culture and sports should be considered in the context of the theories of open, social, ethical and non-commercial marketing, which allows it to be organically included in the management system of not only the commercial, but also the state and public sectors of the physical culture and sports system.

The legitimacy of considering marketing in sports from the standpoint of the theory of open marketing is due to the fact that its subjects (individuals, physical culture and sports organizations and physical culture and sports management bodies) do not operate in the market in isolation, but only through the exchange of information, financial, personnel, material and technical and other resources with each other, with the external environment in relation to them, i.e. are open systems.

Marketing in physical culture and sports is also based on a social and ethical concept that requires the interests of consumers of physical culture and sports services, sports organizations, society as a whole and the state to be observed.

Consideration of marketing in the field of physical culture and sports is also appropriate within the framework of the theory of non-commercial marketing, since the non-commercial sector occupies a dominant position here. A huge part of the consumers of physical culture and sports services are children, teenagers, students, pensioners, and the disabled.

Physical culture and sports work with them is one of the priorities of the state social policy. Under these conditions, the market principle "costs - profits" gives way to the main principle of social policy - "costs - social priorities". In this regard, the marketing of physical culture and sports services can be considered as a special kind of social work. In this context, marketing acts as a factor contributing to the observance and reasonable balance of the principles of economic efficiency and social justice in the management of the physical culture system [4].

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DISCOVERY OF THE ECONOMIC LAW OF THE DOMINANT RISING OF SPIRITUAL NECESSITIES: STRENGTHENING IN MODERN CONDITIONS THE ROLE OF CHARITY OF THE RICH, INCLUDING BILLIONAIRES AND MILLIONAIRES

Uraz Baimuratov

Professor, Director of the Institute of Social Economy and Finance. Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract of the report. Discovery of the economic law of the dominant rising of spiritual necessities: strengthening in modern conditions the role of charity of the rich, including billionaires and millionaires

This scientific law was opened at the Institute of Social Economy and Finance. In 2014, as a result of wide scientific expertise, the International Academy of Authors of Scientific Discoveries and Inventions issued to the author of this article a diploma for discovery No. 62-S. The formula of the discovery means that a previously unknown law of socio-economic harmony has been established, which consists in the dominant rise of moderate spiritual necessities over reasonable material necessities and the desires of individuals, due to real phenomena of the dual world and connection between types of needs. The duality of the world is determined by the priority of one or another type of needs. This topic is described in more detail in an article in the journal "Shygys", 2021, No. 2

**THE ECONOMIC SECURITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF
BUSINESSES DURING CRISIS**

Toghrul Akbarli Ramiz

Lankaran State University, Phd student. AZ4250, Lankaran city, Azerbaijan Republic, Azi Aslanova Alley

It is possible to attain high quality economic growth only by only as a result of effective operations of businesses during information economics. The threats against any country's national security is directly or indirectly dependent on the successful performance of businesses.

The article looked at the theoretical views towards sustainability and economic security concepts, the sustainability of businesses were scrutinized from economic security point of view, the linkage and dependence between sustainability and economic security concepts were investigated and potential macroeconomic opportunities of businesses were identified. The model of ensuring the national economic security of the country requires all economic entities to comply with a single mechanism for protecting national economic interests in the domestic and foreign markets. Rather, the qualitative existence of an economic entity depends on the rules and norms for ensuring the economic security of the state, which has numerous mechanisms for regulating its activities.

As per Resource-functional approach, there are seven ways the economic security of business subjects can be grouped: intellectual-HR; finance, technology, political-legal, eologic, information and power. The best feature of this approach is having complex nature. The supporters of this approach argue that not only the factors which might have the impact on economic security, but also the resource allocation should also be investigated. It can be noted that, this approach also covers the content of the action plans which may lead to the high level economic security of any enterprise.

Another approach over the definition of economic security of businesses is called the decrease of losses and securing the property rights. Although several studies have been conducted, it hasn't been fully investigated how businesses should compete with unfair competition.

Thus, the appearance of unfair competition is associated with the state itself not with the direct result of enterprise acts. According to V. Shlikhov, the losses which arise as a result of not taking the economic interests of the state into account should be treated under the umbrella of costs to eliminate them.

It can be concluded that economic security covers the defence against the negative repercussions of internal and external threats. The comprehensive study of sustainability concept of businesses allows to review its mutual relationship with the concept of economic security. Namely, the state model of economic security requires the following of common mechanism about the preservation of national interest by all business subjects both in local and overseas markets. Moreover, the high quality existence of businesses depend on the norms and rules allowing the provision of economic security of any state. Such dependence of business performance on state's economic policy creates a question: Can a business subject influence the economic security of any state and its economic policymaking? It is obvious that the interest of all physical and legal persons are very important for economic security. Namely, any gap in the performance of business subjects might lead to negative tendencies at macroeconomic dimension. It can also be noted that although there are various kinds of factors influencing the sustainability of business subjects, most of them are not related with the economic security.

Chemical & Material Science

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- *Biochemistry*
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- *Chemical Kinetics & Catalysis*
- *Combustion & Propulsion*
- *Composite Materials*
- *Corrosion*
- *Crystallography & Structural Chemistry*
- *Dispersion Chemistry*
- *Electrochemistry*
- *Inorganic Chemistry*
- *Materials Engineering*
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- *Molecular Modeling*
- *Nanotechnology*
- *Oil, Petroleum & Natural Gas*
- *Organic Chemistry*
- *Polymers & Plastics*

SYNTHESIS OF FULLERENES BY THE ELECTRIC ARC DISCHARGE METHOD

Aimasheva Zhadyra Kenzhebaevna

PhD doctoral student of the NAO Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Ismailov D.V

c.t.s., PhD., Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi, Almaty, Kazakhstan

To date, fullerene is of great interest to scientists around the world. This material has very great prospects for use as additives in various industries. At present, a sufficient number of methods for obtaining fullerenes have been developed. Of the most common, one can note a method based on the synthesis of fullerenes in the presence of an inert gas obtained by the evaporation of graphite. The "separation" of carbon atoms is carried out using an electric arc.

In the course of experimental work in a helium environment, by the method of electric arc sputtering of graphite, the products of a plasma-chemical reaction were obtained at the following discharge parameters: $p=300$ Torr, $U=30$ V and $I=300$ A. It was found that during the synthesis reaction during anode evaporation, on cathode, a deposit of various configurations is formed. Such a deposit can grow both coaxially with the cathode and deviate from its axis, but always coaxially with the anode. It has been established that the deposit in the cross section has two zones - loosened and smooth zones.

In the process of synthesis, carbon vapor in the plasma state, having a temperature of about 12,000 K, escapes from the arc region (interelectrode space) at a speed of 20-25 m/s and reaches the reactor wall in 0.003 seconds, cooling down to room temperature. During this hardening, a number of reactions take place, the mechanisms of which depend on many factors. The obtained carbon black was dissolved in benzene in the experimental setup. The solution was then successively filtered on a filter. The light fractions were filtered what sank to the bottom was filtered on the filter. Then dried at room temperature.

The resulting carbon material was studied using a Quanta 3D 200i scanning electron microscope, Raman spectroscopy and an optical microscope, the results of the study correspond to the reference data, which indicates the presence of C₆₀ and C₇₀ fullerenes.

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BASIC PROBLEMS OF MACHINE TRANSLATION PROGRAMMES

Mammadzada Sevinj Salim

PhD, Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract. Translation process travelled through several stages in its progress, but recently, people have more interest in computer translation that doesn't need any individual author style. With the development of informational technology new computer programmes appeared to simplify the translation process. Unfortunately, such programmes have some disadvantages besides its advantages. The main idea of this thesis is to analyse the main problems of machine translation programmes that translators can come across during the translation process.

Key words: source language, target language, machine translation, wordforms, computer programmes, transformation, metalanguage.

Translation process has very old history. It goes back to the age when people started to live in different tribes and had different languages and speech forms. They had a need to understand each other and some of them used to know several languages of different tribal groups. They were known as the first translators of the history. Translation process played very important role and sociological function in the history allowing to communicate the people of various groups and nations. Expanding the written translation process opened a wide entrance to different cultures of other nations, made it possible to interact with each other and to develop the mutual relations between them.

After the invention and the use of computers, a new kind of translation process – machine translation started to develop. This kind of translation became very useful and helpful for translators. However, besides its advantages it has several problems and disadvantages. It is true that, the more dictionaries you use, the better translation you may have. It means that, the first problem of machine translation is to create rich and big dictionaries for the system. The translation system should differ all the sentences in different contexts. So, the second problem is to teach the system to recognize the real turns of a speech. The sentences for translation are written according to appropriate rules, are translated according to these rules. So, there could be the following problem: to transfer all these rules to the translation programme. All these problems are known as the main problems of machine translation system and the methods of their solution isn't known as far by everyone. [1, p.5-15] So, let's analyse the first problem.

Dictionaries: for qualitative translation it is necessary that practically all the words of the source text can easily be found in a system dictionary and the words that don't exist in this system leave the system without translation, they are transferred to the target language by hand. Such words may affect to the quality of translation. For analysing this word a person uses his or her intellectual abilities that machine translation programme doesn't have. If the meaning of even one word in a sentence is unrecognizable it may spoil all the analysis of a sentence and the result of a translation. A big dictionary is a dictionary that contains many articles, or the dictionary that can recognize many more wordforms from different texts and contexts. [4, p.154-158]

In some systems the full morphological descriptions for all languages have been unically made and successfully used. They contain more than 800 types of wordforms for Russian language, more than 300 types for German and French, and more than 250 for English wordforms. The words with different endings can successfully be translated in these

systems. This model of morphology helped to create the expert system for the user- the creator of a dictionary. [4, p.160-163]

Another problem is **Grammar**: there are two main types of translation systems: TRANSFER and INTERLINGUA. For TRANSFER type of the system the algorithm of translation is formed like the composition of 3 processes; the analysis of the source sentence with the terms of the source language, transformation process of this structure to analogical structure of the target language and the synthesis of the target sentence according to the result structure. For INTERLINGUA type of the system the algorithm of translation is a little bit simple. The analysis of the source sentence with the terms of metalanguage and the synthesis of a target sentence from metastructure. The main problem of this type is to create metalanguage and to describe the natural language with appropriate words. Stylistical and grammatical mistakes of machine translation are perfectly compensated by a person himself. [2, p.67-75]

Analysis of machine translation. When we work with translation programmes we can meet with a line of problems while translating the text. Lexical analysis of translated texts showed that the large number of electronic translators can translate simple parts of speech, but make mistakes while translating some speech forms and grammatical structures. The main problem of machine translation programmes is a wrong translation of the words that have different meanings. Grammatical analysis of texts shows that electronic translator can translate the words in plural and singular, but has difficulties with the translation of verbs of different languages with different endings. Many factors contribute to the difficulty of machine translation, including sentences with multiple grammatical structures, words with different meanings, compound words, missing terms, cultural differences, verbs made up of two words and so on. So, computers can not replace the human translator in many ways. [3, p.222-227] Should we use machine translation then?- Yes, we should. When we translate the texts belonged to literature we can get the rough copy of the target text that can easily be rechecked and corrected by a person who has less language knowledge of original text, but has better literacy knowledge. As for technical texts that are written in the frames of technical context, it is not always necessary to make corrections in the target texts. Machine translation systems usually need correction, because of different problems mentioned above. Due to the lack of phrase identification and increasing intelligence, the substitution of words cannot produce reliable translation results. That's why machine translation systems should have edition and correction resources. Some linguists are against of machine translation programmes. They think, it is 15% of meaningful result, but 85% of foolish. Such kind of programmes, they think, are only for technical documents and for their translation. [5, p.40-48]

Overall, is it useful to use machine translation programmes or to pay to human translator to get a proper translation? Some companies choose the first, others choose the second choice. The first ones think that despite of small difficulties, machine translation programmes can cope with unnecessary and simple problems. With machine translation they are able to translate entire document at the click of a button and at very low cost, and they ask themselves why one might even bother to hire a human translator for their translation work? As there are several problems that come from machine translation that can only be overcome by hiring a human translator. Others think that no machine translation programme can compensate or replace the intellectual human one. Though machine translation has benefits of quickly translating content at a low cost, in all reality it is not the best solution for most of our needs. [5, p.200-210]

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**AUTONOMOUS CONTROLLED UNINHABITED UNDERWATER VEHICLE IN
CONDITIONS OF HYDRODYNAMIC INSTABILITY USING SIMULATION IN
MATLAB**

Makhabbat Krivolapova

Victor Ivel

Yuliya Gerassimova

Keywords: Autonomous unmanned underwater vehicle, AUV, mathematical model, structural model, Simulink simulation, control system, hydrodynamic instability.

This study reveals the problems of using autonomous controlled uninhabited vehicles in conditions of hydrodynamic instability. As a result, the following was developed: a mathematical model and a block diagram of the AUV control system model, taking into account the influence of hydrodynamic instability, and a model of the control system was created in the Simulink package of the MATLAB system, and the created system was simulated.

One of the options for the use of autonomous controlled uninhabited vehicles is underwater marine uninhabited vehicles (AUVs - autonomous uninhabited underwater vehicles). At the moment, these devices are effectively used in scientific research, emergency rescue operations at sea, when performing search tasks and other types of complex work.

An analysis of the parameters of motion and the environment reveals a causal relationship between various types of hydrodynamic instability, emerging forces and moments with heading angles, roll and trim of the AUV [1].

The basic model for the study of dynamic stability will be a simplified mathematical model of the scientific school of the Moscow State Technical University. N.E. Bauman. In this model, the main criteria for the stability of the AUV control are: stable maintenance of the specified motion parameters regardless of the state of the external environment, constant accident-free controllability of the AUV at all operating depths and courses [2].

The modeling method used to study the dependence of the change in the heading angle of attack on the applied forces and moments of hydrodynamic instability: the finite volume method for a volumetric body placed in a liquid medium and moving at a given speed [3].

The AUV control model being created uses three coordinate systems (CS) associated with the underwater vehicle: - fixed coordinate system of the Earth OXYZ; - coordinate system associated with the direction of movement of the apparatus Axyz (velocity coordinate system); - coordinate system tied to the AUV body with zero at the center of mass $Ax_1y_1z_1$. Used angular parameters in the description of the model: heading angle φ ; course roll θ , AUV trim ψ , angle of attack α , drift angle β , trajectory angles χ , Φ , ϑ . Used forces and moments: residual buoyancy P , longitudinal and transverse restoring moments of stability, respectively M_ϕ and M_θ , water drag force R , water drag moment M_R [4].

Modeling of the motion trajectory of an autonomous uninhabited floating vehicle will be carried out in the coordinate system associated with the AUV body with zero at the center of mass[6]. The modeling environment is a viscous fluid that cannot be compressed. So a change in the heading angle α_{course} (both an increase and a decrease) will cause a phase advance (due to the inertia of the liquid medium) proportional to the change in the velocity angle α_{corr} .

Based on the analysis of the mathematical equation of motion of an underwater vehicle under conditions of environmental instability, a block diagram of the axial control is drawn up. In the figure, the values of the coefficients correspond to the fundamental formula, mathematical operands and operations are replaced by connections and blocks corresponding

to operations. Here you can use the Abs block from the Simulink library, however, when building a block diagram, the principles of classical control theory were used and, in our opinion, it would not be entirely correct to include blocks from Simulink in such a structure.

As a result of the calculations and development, the model was obtained. The system consists of three channels: a model in the projection on the OX axis, a model in the projection on the OY axis, and a model with rotation. As in the case of the mathematical model, the model in the Simulink program was compiled on the basis of the structural model of the control system and, from a technical point of view, fully corresponds to it. On the model in the Simulink system, the operating units corresponding to the mathematical operations in the formula are replaced with blocks with the corresponding function. The values of the functions correspond to the calculated values of the formulas. Connections between blocks and modules repeat the connections of the block diagram [10].

The analysis of the created system in the Simulink program by modeling showed that there are no deviations from the trajectory in the base coordinate system even under conditions of strong external influences.

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ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГИДРАВЛИЧЕСКОГО ПРИВОДА К РОТАЦИОННЫМ РЕЖУЩИМ АППАРАТАМ СЕНОКОСИЛКЕ

Алиев Эльдар Айдын оглы

Диссертант, Научно - Исследовательский институт – Агро механика

Багиров Байрам Мухаммад оглы

д.т.н., профессор, Азербайджанский Технологический Университет

Основным рабочим органом сенокосилок является режущий аппарат. Работа косилок заключается в обеспечении процесса непосредственного скашивания травы и расстелет скошенной травы по рядам слоями. Согласно Агро требований с одной стороны, траву следует стричь таким образом, чтобы после сбора урожая была возможность для повторного интенсивного роста травы на этом участке. С другой стороны, трава должна быть подстрижена так, чтобы она была максимум по одинаковой той же заранее установленной высоте, чтобы масса в поле могла быть собрана без потерь. Обеспечение этих требований в основном зависит от соотношения скоростей между режущим лезвием и его поступательной скоростью по полю.

Обычно сена косилка агрегируется с трактором, и в таких косилочных агрегатах - трактор + косилка, вращательное движение ножа косилки передается от вала отбора мощности (ВОМ) трактора. Ныне во всех косилочных аппаратах эта осуществляется механическим приводом, При этом между ВОМ и режущего ножа используются различных элементов передачи: зубчатая, шестеренчатые, цепные. ременные и т.д. В существующих косилках их ножи вращаются, постоянной скорости и нет возможности, изменить их скорости по мере изменение поступательной скорости трактора. Вместе с тем в процессе скашивания скорость работы трактора, может изменяться, в пределах от 1,5-5,0 м/с ,то ест - 5,4 - 18 км/час.

У ротационных косилок при скашивании травы в косилке каждый вращающимся режущий орган-нож лезвием, изгибает травы как продольно, так и перпендикулярно по направлению движения машины, причем величина этих изгибов меняется в зависимости от скорости вращения лезвия и от поступательной скорости машины.

В зависимости от соотношения скорости машины к скорости ножа у этих машин могут иметь места как не до рез, так и - двух, - трех и т.д. резание одно и то же растения. В первом случае увеличивается высота резание растений - увеличивается потери урожая, а во втором случае увеличивается затрат энергии процессе скашивания растений. Поэтому во время кошения необходимо следить за тем, чтобы лезвие ножа режущего аппарата было равномерно нагружено по всей своей длине, чтобы избежать неубранной площади и двойной площади кошения. Для этого скорость лезвия должна соответственно увеличиваться по мере увеличения поступательной скорости машины. В существующих косилках механическим приводам эта требования не обеспечивается. Установлено что для обеспечения этого требования можно использовать гидравлической привод вращательного движения, что позволит методом дросселированные подачи рабочий жидкости привода ножа по ходу движения и оперативно изменять скорость ножа из кабины трактора.

Нами в Азербайджанском Государственном Аграрном Университете – Научно Исследовательском Институте – Агро механике разработан гидропривод ротационной сенокосилки, который по мере увеличение поступательной скорости движение агрегата, дает возможность, прямо в кабине трактора изменить скорости движения ножа режущего аппарата, в соответствие скорости машины. Это позволяет во всех

режимах работы косил очного агрегата по полю уменьшит, потери урожая от высоты скашивания и затрат энергии скашивания 10-12% и больше.

МАЛОГАБАРИТНОЙ КОРМОСМЕСИТЕЛ КОНЦКОРМА ДЛЯ МАЛЫЙ ФЕРМ И ДОМОХОЗЯЙСТВ

Вердиева Ламан Фаиг кызы

Докторант, Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет

Багиров Байрам Мухаммед оглы

д.т.н., проф., Азербайджанский Технологический Университет

В полноценной кормосмеси концкорма и их различные комбинации считаются группой полезных смесей с высокой калорийностью в сравнительно меньшем объеме. Эта смесь и входящие в ее состав концкормовые компоненты – кукуруза, пшеница, ячмень и др., являются, доступны каждому хозяйству, и имеет соответствующую стабильную кормовую ценность. Такие комбикорма из этих материалов в настоящее время производятся в основном на крупных комбикормовых цехах, заводах и фабриках. Опыт развитых стран и анализ условий республики Азербайджан показывают, что поставка кормов, их хранение, транспортировка до и после обработки продукта и т. д. затраты труда, технических и энергетических затрат, приводит к повышенной себестоимости полученного продукта не менее чем в 1,5 - 2 раза по сравнению с приготовлением этой продукции в каждом хозяйстве. Если учесть что из всех хозяйств республики Азербайджан более 85% составляют малые фермеры и домохозяйства то поэтому в таких местных условиях каждому фермеру, крестьянину и домохозяйству выгоднее приготовить комбикорм из кормовых компонентов собственной кормовой базы - в первую очередь фуражные зерна. Однако отсутствия научно обоснованных малогабаритных технических средств является серьезным препятствием в разрешении данной проблемы в селе. Важно и актуально разработать малогабаритное устройство для приготовления полноценной концентрированной кормосмеси, позволяющее экономить материальные, и энергетические ресурсы. Разработанный нами такое устройство в местных условиях может измельчать зерновых компонентов до одинакового размера, смешивать их между собой и с добавками минералами, витаминами, перед скармливанием животных. При этом один из важных показателей качества - степень однородности смесей - повышается по мере дробления зерен на одни и те же фракции. На одном таком объекте можно получить кормовую смесь, подходящую как для крупного рогатого скота, так и для других животных и птиц, с экономией материально- энергетических ресурсов.

Health & Medical Science

- Addiction
- AIDS & HIV
- Alternative & Traditional Medicine
- Anesthesiology
- Audiology, Speech & Language Pathology
- Bioethics
- Biomedical Technology
- Cardiology
- Child & Adolescent Psychology
- Clinical Laboratory Science
- Communicable Diseases
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- Dermatology
- Developmental Disabilities
- Diabetes
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- Epidemiology
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- Gynecology & Obstetrics
- Health & Medical Sciences (general)
- Heart & Thoracic Surgery
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- Virology
- Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery

TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS

Kamilov Khaydar

MD,DSc, Professor, Head of the Department of Hospital Therapeutic Dentistry, Tashkent State Dental Institute

Bakhramova Farangiz

Doctoral student of the Department of Hospital Therapeutic Dentistry, Tashkent State Dental Institute

Usmanova Lazzat

Teaching Assistant of the Department of Hospital Therapeutic Dentistry, Tashkent State Dental Institute

Introduction. A correct diagnostics of recurrent aphthous stomatitis (RAS, sometimes also called recurrent oral ulcers or ulcers) is a central element of dentistry issues. Aphthous ulcers have been carefully defined so that they can be differentiated from many other types of recurrent oral ulcers that are not associated with systemic abnormalities (M.Kh. Ibragimova, 2019). Objectively, the prevalence rate is incredibly high, but if RAS is defined as more than two spontaneously occurring episodes per year, then the average prevalence in the population is about 10%, which seems reasonable. Many studies struggle with definitions and ask if subjects ever had mouth ulcers. Reported estimates range from 1.5 to 28% in different parts of the world according to the WHO, suggesting that there may be genetic differences that account for these geographic differences. Current evidence suggests that RAS may be the result of an abnormal cascade of cytokines in the oral mucosa, which leads to a cell-mediated immune response directed to the focal area of the oral mucosa (Alimova D.M., 2021).

Material and research methods. 30 patients with chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis of the oral mucosa were examined at the age of 25-80 years at the Department of Hospital Therapeutic Dentistry of the Tashkent State Dental Institute, in 2017-2020. All the patients had RAS treatment using the infrared spectrum of PDT.

Results. Before treatment, all studied patients complained of pain and discomfort in the oral cavity, aggravated by the intake of spicy and acidic foods, 75% complained of a burning sensation of the oral cavity, 35% had hypersalivation. Treatment of patients with PDT led to the complete elimination of complaints already on the 5th day. As PDT was exposed to the erosive surface, the level of pain intensity decreased. The most pronounced decrease in the intensity of pain syndrome was revealed in the first three days from the start of therapy. Their epithelialization rate averaged 3.5 days. Another important criterion for the effectiveness of HRAS treatment is the duration of remission, which was 120 ± 21.3 days with the use of 1 course of PDT, after three courses of application it was 146 ± 32.5 days.

Conclusions. Thus, photodynamic therapy can be considered an important key to improving the treatment of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis and indeed increasing the effectiveness of its treatment.

BIOETHICAL PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL STAFF IN PERIPHERAL CLINICS OF GEORGIA

Giorgi Parulava

Professor, Faculty of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Georgia

It is well known that the main object of study of bioethics is the moral aspect of the relationship between physician and patient. An alienated relationship between the patient and the physician in terms of protecting human rights and honor is its starting point and lays within its foundation.

To the outside observer, even with the unaided eye, it is easily visible how this issue is neglected in the clinics and dispensaries of Georgian cities and other settlements.

In order to study the given problem, as a subject we chose the "Rukhi State Hospital", located near the border of Russian occupied territory, in the Georgian controlled part of the land. A survey method was used in the research. The survey was conducted among physicians, active and former patients, with the participation of 72 people, including 13 physicians and 49 patients. The question was about how satisfied patients were with the staff, their behavior, their attitude towards them. Also, how comfortable doctors feel in dealing with patients. The analysis of the survey results was performed in the statistical program SPSS 28 (Trial Version). The study included materials published in the recent scientific literature.

Based on the analysis of the results of the survey, we found that the majority of medical staff - 90% - do not understand the basic principles and rules of bioethics, which can be used by doctors and medical professionals in general to understand and solve the most acute moral problems. The following principles: "Do good", "Do not hurt", "Principle of justice", "Respect for patient autonomy" do not work in the above institution and there are many examples to prove this.

The norms of biomedical ethics, which play a particularly important role in regulating the relationship between medical staff and the patient is also incomprehensible to them. This is what experts call bioethical rules. They are more private than the principles and are known as the rule of truth. The rule of confidentiality and the rule of informed consent.

In the scientific literature, bioethics theorists are actively discussing the question of what harm can be done to a patient if the physician ignores the basic principles and rules of bioethics. In this regard, they distinguish the several types of so-called "harm": 1. When the damage is caused by a low qualification of the doctor, which determines his wrong action; 2. The damage is caused due to malicious intent for the purpose of self-interest; 3. Damage is caused by objective necessity in a particular situation; 4. Harm is caused by the inactivity of the doctor when he refuses to help the patient for an unknown reason. The analysis of the accumulated material showed that out of above mentioned types, the low qualification of the doctor takes the place in most cases. He lacks the ability to differentiate between infectious patients. In particular, to a room where one patient is already in its final stage of curing from the virus, an another patient is brought, which increased the risk of re-infecting the first patient with another variant of the virus. Therefore, it is about the doctor's moral responsibility for the harm he has done to the patient through his wrong and careless actions. Especially if he is considered an experienced and qualified doctor. In fact, due to low qualification, this doctor is unable to logically analyze and understand the situation, thus makes decisions that are detrimental to the patient.

Studies have shown that it was also common to find a form of harm related to informing the patient about his health condition and probable prognosis at the moment. The

attending physician and the doctors on duty avoided talking about the details of the illness. Meanwhile, bioethics requires that both parties in the physician-patient relationship to have equal rights. The doctor is obliged to fully inform the patient of the necessary details at his hand. The patient should be aware of his state of health, what are the dynamics of the course of the disease, if the disease progresses or the degree of recovery increases, what medical procedures does he need for further treatment, are these procedures associated with any kind of danger, are there any risks involved, if so, what is their share, etc. It should be noted, however, that telling the truth is required not only of the physician but also of the patient and determines their moral responsibility. In our opinion, this factor points out the low qualification of the physicians working here, who by all means fail to understand the psycho-emotional state of the patient.

There have also been cases of patients being harmed by a doctor by passing medical information about a patient's health condition to a third party without the patient's consent, which goes against the generally accepted postulate of "protection of medical confidentiality." Unfortunately, they cannot explain their actions in the context of "inevitable harm". Thus, in the context of Georgia's application for European Union (EU) membership, the health sector needs to pay special attention to the issues of bioethical education of physicians and medical staff in general, which is on very high level in the EU.

Based on the analysis of the results of the research, we consider it necessary in bioethical education to:

- Implement qualification enhancement courses via cathedrae/departments of bioethics of universities of the relevant field.
- Create 4 credit special program in bioethics.
- Procedural issues be handled by the Ministry of Health of Georgia.

STRUCTURAL PECULIARITIES OF PRIMARY SENSORY NEURONS

Aliyarbayova Aygun Aliyar

PhD, Senior Teacher of the Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku

Sultanova Tamilla Ahliman

PhD, Associated Professor of the Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku

Mehraliyeva Gulshan Akbar

PhD, Senior Teacher of the Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku

Sadiqova Gulnara Huseyn

PhD, Senior Teacher of the Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku

Qurbanova Shahana Qazanfar

Assistant of the Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Azerbaijan Medical University, Baku

Keywords: sensory neuron, dorsal root ganglia, light microscope, morphometry.

Introduction. The primary sensory neurons whose cell body placed in dorsal root ganglion has a significant clinical application, particularly in its association with neuropathic pain. Taken into account that primary sensory neurons are important station in the somatosensory, especially in pain pathways, its morphofunctional peculiarities investigation is very important.

Aim. The goal of this study was exploration specific morphological feature of primary sensory neurons, as well as to establish the morphofunctional heterogeneity in neurons of the dorsal root ganglia.

Materials and methods. The object of the study was dorsal root ganglia purchased from 20 white rats with a weight of 220 - 240 grams. The animals grew up in scientific laboratory with a special pathogen-free condition. All procedures complied with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care established by the Azerbaijan Medical University. Into the tail vein of research animals was administered 0.5 ml physiological salt solution. Then animals decapitated under ketamine anesthesia; dorsal root ganglia removed from the soft tissue. The specimen had been fixated in solution that contains 2% paraformaldehyde, 2% glutaraldehyde and 0.1% picric acid in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After the postfixation in 1% osmium acid solution the specimen embedded into Spurr and Araldit-Epon blocks. Obtained from blocks on ultratomes LKB -III, Leica EM UC7 semithin sections (1-2 μ m) stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin or with toluidine blue. After examination with Latimet (Leitz) microscope necessary parts of images were taken on Pixera (USA) digital camera.

Results and discussions. By using a light microscope, we revealed that primary sensory neuronal cell bodies with nucleus, nucleolus in thoracic and lumbar levels of dorsal root ganglia of the rat are isolated by densely stained connective tissue capsule. On histological slide we have detected two type staining cytoplasm of neurons: light and dark. No regularities found in the histotopographic positions, as well as in size of the light and dark neurons. A lot of number satellite glial cells nucleus are visible in close proximity of both neurons. On the histological slide around of large sized neuron detect outnumber of nucleus of satellite glial cells than small sized neuron. There was no correlation between neuronal

soma diameters and staining of cytoplasm, because on slide visible any type of cell size: small, medium, large can exhibit light or dark cytoplasm.

Conclusion. Summarizing the upward information, there is no morphological basis for the separation of primary sensory neurons of dorsal root ganglion into two groups: small dark cells (SDC) and large light cells (LLC).

**OBJECTIVE APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF HYPERTROPHIC
CARDIOMYOPATHY WITH OBSTRUCTION OF THE OUTFLOW TRACT OF
THE LEFT VENTRICLE**

Abzaliev Kuat Bayandyevich

Research Institute of Cardiology and Internal Medicine, doctoral student of the Higher School Al-Farabi KazNU

Tuleutaev Rustem Mukhtarovich

Research Institute of Cardiology and Internal Medicine

Pakhomenko Elena Nikolaevna

student of the Higher School Al-Farabi KazNU

According to a new method (patent pending) of septal myectomy, 10 patients with left ventricular outflow tract obstruction (LVOT) with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy were operated on. Mutations in the genes of sarcolemmal proteins were found in 80% of patients. On ultrasound, the systolic pressure gradient in the outflow tract of the left ventricle is $> 50 - 75 < \text{mm. rt. Art.}$ was in 1 (10%), $> 75 - 100 < \text{mm. rt. Art.}$ - in 8 (80%) and more than 100 mm. rt. Art. – only in 1 (10%) patient. The patients also underwent computed tomography to obtain an anatomical picture. Intraoperatively, according to the results of transesophageal ultrasound, there was a significant decrease in the LVOT pressure gradient: $< 5 \text{ mm. rt. Art.}$ - in 5 (50%), $> 5 - 15 < \text{mm. rt. Art.}$ - in 5 (50%) patients. In these patients, during ultrasound, we performed speckle tracking in a longitudinal projection in a two-three and four-chamber position, as well as in three projections along the short axis at the level of the mitral valve, papillary muscles and the apex of the left ventricle to obtain information on transverse twisting. Having obtained the maximum strain data, we calculated the post-systolic strain, which is characterized by myocardial dyssynchrony, evaluated rotation (displacement of myocardial segments along the short axis around the long axis), twist (difference between the movement of the apex and basal parts of the left ventricle), twisting gradient (calculated as twisting in relation to the length of the left ventricle). To find the area and volume of the excised part of the myocardium, we made mathematical calculations using the formula. On average, according to mathematical calculations, the volume of the excised part of the myocardium was $3.2 + 1.7 \text{ cm}^3$.

Thus, for an objective approach to the treatment of hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, we calculated the area and volume of the excised part by building mathematical models. Having conducted an ultrasound study, we objectively confirmed the presence of myocardial fiber dyssynchrony, which manifested itself as a segmental change in the longitudinal strain in the form of a slowdown in systolic shortening of the myocardium.

POSSIBILITIES OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION AS A WAY OUT OF POSTNATAL DEPRESSION

Turegeldieva Akzharkyn Serikbaevna

PhD-doctoral student, "8D10201 - Social work", al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Republic of Kazakhstan

Ключевые слова: постнатальная депрессия, помощь социального работника, «Дом мамы», социальная адаптация.

Key words: postnatal depression, social worker's help, "Mom's House", social adaptation.

Рождение ребенка является радостным и счастливым событием в жизни каждой женщины. Но если это обычная благополучная женщина, живущая в семье и не имеющая материальных, социальных и других проблем. Если же это слишком юная роженица, не имеющая поддержки со стороны любимого человека и семьи; если это женщина, не знающая куда пойти с ребенком из роддома; если это женщина, не имеющая средств к существованию и т.д. – в таких случаях зачастую после рождения ребенка женщина впадает в депрессию, не находя выхода из создавшейся проблемной ситуации. Большую роль здесь должна сыграть помощь близких, друзей или общества. В Казахстане функционирует сеть «Домов мамы» - «Ана үйі» - "Mom's House", в который может обратиться каждая женщина, имеющая проблемы послеродового периода. Координаторы этой организации оказывают широкий спектр помощи женщинам, способствуя их выходу из депрессии и социальной адаптации. Это может быть:

- 1) юридическая помощь в оформлении документов и получении положенных государственных выплат;
- 2) информирование женщин о системе социальной поддержки со стороны негосударственных организаций;
- 3) помощь в трудоустройстве;
- 4) помощи в поиске и устройстве на курсы по получению востребованной в обществе профессии;
- 5) помощь в постановке на учет ребенка для получения места в детском саду;
- 6) в случае необходимости – помощь в организации лечения ребенка.

Эти и другие мероприятия способствуют выходу женщин, попавших в тяжелую жизненную ситуацию, из депрессивного состояния и мотивируют их на стремление к полноценной самостоятельной жизни.

USE AND EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF INDIVIDUAL ZIRCONIUM POSTS

Nigmatova Nigora Rakhmatullaevna

Department of Faculty of Orthopedic Dentistry, Tashkent State Dental Institute

Relevance. Despite the use in everyday practice of modern technologies for prosthetics in patients with significant or complete destruction of the crown part of the tooth, the frequency of complications when using cast stump pin inlays remains high. According to studies by domestic and foreign authors, the most common complications include root splitting, which can be caused by thinning of the canal walls, as well as incorrect pin geometry and the design of the cast stump insert itself.

Purpose of the study. Development and evaluation of the effectiveness of a new design of zirconium dioxide individual pin for a single-rooted tooth.

Materials and methods of research. Clinical studies were carried out in the clinics of the Department of Faculty Orthopedic Dentistry of the Tashkent State Dental Institute. The material for the analysis and conclusions was the examination data of 21 patients with a defect in the crown part of the tooth. Of these, 13 (61.9%) men and 8 (38.1%) women aged 18 to 45 years. The main group of patients were divided into 2 groups: the 1st group of patients with complete destruction of the crown part of the tooth, we made the developed pin tooth design from an individual zirconium dioxide pin - 12 patients; and the 2nd group of patients who were made pin teeth by the traditional method - 9 patients.

All patients underwent clinical, radiological, photometric, laboratory, functional and statistical methods of research.

Research results. The objectives of the study included the development of a new type of dental pin, equipped with a removable head, easy to perform, convenient to use, as well as expanding the range of dental pinning tools.

The problem was solved by the fact that in a dental pin with an inlay for a single-root tooth, made in the form of a screw, consisting of two parts: intra-root and extra-root. The root part is made in the form of a truncated cone with a thread, the extra root part has a cut for screwing the pin, the extra root part is made in the form of a cone.

We have proposed pin options with different parameters for the length, diameter and pitch of the threaded section (Patent of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No. FAP 01787 dated 03/18/2021).

The dental pin is made monolithic, while the root (apical) part and the extra root part for the crown (in the form of an abutment) are separate sections of a solid screw equipped with a removable screw with a head. Such a dental pin is used for one-stage fixation of artificial crowns.

The combination of two functions (plugs for the mouth of the canal and the shaper of the crown part of the tooth) in one extra-root part of the specified dental pin simplifies and speeds up the treatment process. Removable stump head allows its replacement in case of wear or damage.

The pin tooth developed by us is intended for prosthetics of premolars and anterior teeth in the absence of a natural crown in them, but while maintaining its root at the gum level with a well-passable canal.

High-tech equipment is used for the manufacture of zirconium pins. The process is fully automated, takes place without human intervention according to the CAD\CAM method. The computer processes the received information and creates a virtual future design.

The results of the clinical use of the pin design proposed by us as a support for an all-ceramic crown showed high efficiency; no cases of root or structure splits in any part of it, pin or crown unfixation were noted during the entire observation period. The ceramic crown, core composite and post remain almost unchanged in color. The only problem, in our opinion, not related to constructive materials, are cases of gingival recession, atrophy of marginal bone tissue.

Findings. Thus, based on the anatomical and topographic features of the anterior teeth, the manufacture of a threaded structure of pin teeth from zirconium dioxide produced by 3D milling has been scientifically substantiated.

The results of the clinical use of the pin design proposed by us as a support for an all-ceramic crown showed high efficiency.

The proposed pin design can be widely used in modern practical healthcare.

Humanities, Literature & Arts

- *African Studies & History*
- *American Literature & Studies*
- *Asian Studies & History*
- *Canadian Studies & History*
- *Chinese Studies & History*
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- *Religion*
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- *Visual Arts*

THE CONTEXT OF "LANGUAGE AND CULTURE" IN TEXTBOOKS OF KAZAKH AND TURKISH LANGUAGES (BASED ON ZOONYMIC VOCABULARY)

Rayeva Assemgul

L.N .Gumilyov, Eurasian National University, PhD student, Kazakhstan, Nur-Sultan

Keywords: linguoculturology, linguoculturology, zoonymic vocabulary, zoonymic code

This article examines the relevance of the context "language and culture" in teaching Kazakh and Turkish languages. The main part of the article examines the works of domestic and foreign scientists on the topic, discusses the inextricable link between culture and language, on the basis of which the importance of teaching culture through language, language through culture is determined. Textbooks of Kazakh and Turkish languages were taken as objects of research. According to textbooks for teaching Turkic languages, a statistical analysis of the significance of teaching national and cultural vocabulary, including zoonymic vocabulary, was carried out, in particular, the content of texts (basic, additional, explanatory) related to zoonyms, the availability of related materials (exercises and tasks, analysis, synthesis, selection and questions for systematization), types of tasks for texts (creative, practical, project, practice-oriented) related to zoonyms. The analysis and discussion of ways of expressing and studying the cultural life of a native speaker forming language skills in language learners through the development of zoonymic vocabulary shows the importance of research. As a result of the research, the conclusion is made about the importance of taking into account the cultural life of the nation when studying concepts related to animal names in the lexical fund of the Turkic peoples. According to the results of statistical analysis, it is proposed that textbooks for teaching Kazakh and Turkish languages include more culturological texts and text tasks related to the animal world. Teaching Kazakh and Turkish languages on the basis of the relationship between "language and culture" is recognized as worthy of today's educational paradigms.

KINDRED NAMES AS PART OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL CONCEPT

Rakhimova Dinara

Eurasian National University after L.N. Gumilyov, Faculty of Philology, Department of Kazakh Linguistics, 2nd year PhD student, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan

Keywords: Kindred names, common Turkic vocabulary, primordial words, linguoculturology

Abstract. The article deals with kindred names that are part of the general Turkic vocabulary. They are also considered the basis of the vocabulary. The linguistic, folk, and cultural character of kindred names is described, i.e. the article deals with the linguoculturological, ethnolinguistic, and cognitive aspects of kindred names. Kindred names are included in the oldest layer of the language. After all, any person living in society, being a member of the social environment, enters into a family relationship. This indicates that in the event of any phenomenon or relationship, a name or nomenclature is necessarily assigned to him/her. Therefore, kindred names in the lexical fund of the Turkic peoples as a whole are represented in a number of primordial words. Our research paper provides a commentary on the primordial Turkic vocabulary, the primordial vocabulary of the Kazakh language. The definition of the term "primordial word" has been made and attention has been paid to the classification of the common Turkic vocabulary. As a result, the conceptual field, semantic space of names denoting kinship in the Kazakh language are described.

EDUCATION BASED ON THE CREATION OF A PROJECT (PBL) THROUGH THE FORMATION OF AN INDIVIDUAL'S INTEREST IN EDUCATION, DEVELOPMENT, AND ACHIEVING RESULTS

Bimbetova Zamira Asilkhanovna

Teacher of Pedagogical Sciences, teacher-researcher of the highest category, Teacher of Kazakh language and literature of the school-Lyceum "BINOM-" Tanyim", Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan

Keywords: PBL, pedagogy, team, communicative, research, problem Question, final product, auura, factor, idea, position, hypothesis, solidarity, ability, creativity, creativity.

Abstract. The relevance of the article lies in the importance of PBL (project-based education) in human life, evidence that the student's communicative interaction with others through research can serve as a basis for the method of Education. The need for project-based learning in the modern educational system of research is the only relevant method that arouses the student's interest. In the main part of the article, there are pedagogical practical arguments that combine and increase the phenomena of real life with knowledge that increases the student's interest in the subject, arouses desire, love for knowledge, and gives strength.

In my opinion, it is quite possible that in the process of the project, the intellectual abilities of the child will be formed from the cognitive conflict that arises around the problem question and the true picture of life, and the argument of different opinions. This conflict is a struggle for the knowledge, a struggle for answers to problematic questions. In the same struggle, the child's knowledge becomes more and more completed.

In search of answers, understanding is formed in the course of the problem situation, learning to work together with others, teamwork, learn to analyze their work, get used to asking questions, conduct surveys, conduct research, work on the solution of the problem, give a creative opinion, create a hypothesis. Pedagogical experience has shown that the student's interest in the PBL process is aroused.

Students studying on the basis of a project exchanges experience with each other, get along well, establish friendship and solidarity, discover their abilities, and develop their creativity. A common idea is born, sought in the same direction, discussed, re-evaluated each other, each tries to prove his position as a result of which, having analyzed, the student makes one common decision and presents the final product.

During the PBL process, the student is on the very front of learning: the child expands the field, learns to fight, defends his position, adapts to the culture of communication.

1. knowledge base / formation of knowledge /
2. work / performer / control / self-education /
3. motivation and entrepreneurship
4. development of new innovations
- 5.the importance of social and contextual factors in education.

The experience of instilling a student with life skills by creating a project that corresponds to the theme of the program, the ability to apply it, and the ability to show the relevance were recognized as an important part in the development of the project.

Life Sciences & Earth Sciences

- *Agronomy & Crop Science*
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- *Animal Husbandry*
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- *Biodiversity & Conservation Biology*
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- *Sustainable Energy*
- *Virology*
- *Wood Science & Technology*
- *Zoology*

ARID LANDSCAPES OF KAZAKHSTAN: MODERN STATE AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT

Akpambetova Kamshat Makpalbaevna

Candidate of Geographical Sciences, Professor, Karaganda Buketov University, Kazakhstan

Amanbek Zhainagul

Master of Natural Sciences, Karaganda Buketov University, Kazakhstan

Muksinov Ernat Bikaidarovich

Master of Natural Sciences, Karaganda Buketov University, Kazakhstan

Dry, shallow and desert lands of different continents have always attracted the attention of scientists. Historically, interest has changed along with the socio-economic conditions of human life and the scientific tasks of researchers. Initially trade, military and educational purposes prevailed. Later, the most developed feudal and then capitalist states tried to draw the desert lands into the field of their colonial aspirations. Attracted mineral resources, some deserts were used for political or economic penetration into neighboring countries. Military bases and cities arose, from where roads were laid to the inner parts of the continents.

The modern development of deserts and the arid zone in general leads to the transformation of the landscapes of Kazakhstan. Drilling wells, mines, urban settlements, roads and power lines appeared among the sands. Arid landscapes turned out to be the testing ground on which some theoretical problems arose and were studied: the origin of deserts and their paleogeographic development, the study of various types of sandy relief and so on.

The formation and development of arid landscapes in Kazakhstan depend on the distribution of heat and moisture on the Earth, the zonality of the geographical envelope, as well. The zonal distribution of temperatures and atmospheric pressure determines the peculiarity of the winds and the general circulation of the atmosphere. The deserts and semi-deserts of Kazakhstan are distinguished by high summer temperatures, low annual precipitation, lack of surface runoff, a large role of eolian processes, groundwater salinity and uneven rainfall. One of the features of distribution is the insular nature of their geographical location. However, despite the locality, the arid landscapes of Kazakhstan can be considered as vast natural categories with all their characteristic environmental conditions.

WATER-COASTAL VEGETATION AND ALGOFLORA OF KORGALZHYN LAKES

Zadagali Aizhan

Master's Degree, 3rd year doctoral student of L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Zhamangara Aizhan

Candidate of Biological Sciences, deputy director for science of Astana Botanical Garden, a branch of the RSE on the REM "Institute of Botany and Phytointroduction" C FW of the MEGNR of the RK

Omarbayeva Aynur

PhD, "Botanical Garden of Astana" - senior researcher of the Astana Botanical Garden, a branch of the RSE on the REM "Institute of Botany and Phytointroduction" CFW of the MEGNR of the RK

Sovkhozova Karlygash

2nd year master's student of Astana International University

Korgalzhyn State Reserve was established in 1968. This natural complex is included in the International Ramsar list and the UNESCO Natural Heritage List. In 2012, it was included in the UNESCO list of natural reserves. The reason for the weakening of the biocenosis on the territory can be chemical contamination, instability of the hydrochemical and hydrobiological structure. Therefore, it is always important to study the water-coastal and aquatic vegetation of Korgalzhyn lakes. It occupies an important place in the comprehensive monitoring of the natural complex.

The Tengiz-Korgalzhyn lake system is affected by toxic substances coming from the Nura riverbed, where waste water from Temirtau-Karaganda industrial sites flows.

Excessive intake of phosphorus compounds in the form of mineral fertilizers from deposits with surface runoff, as well as some industrial waste, leads to uncontrolled growth of plant biomass in reservoirs, changes in the trophic level of reservoirs. This leads to eutrophic changes in hydrocenoses, the predominance of decomposition processes and, accordingly, the increase in turbidity, mineralization of water, and the growth of bacteria.

Sholak, Yessey, Kokay, Sultankeldy, Asaubalyk lakes are the main and auxiliary lakes of the Korgalzhyn lake system.

Swampy vegetation of korgalzhyn natural objects is concentrated near Lake Shores and riverbeds. On the shores of korgalzhyn Lakes, the dominant herbaceous plants include common reed (*Phragmites australis*), reedmace (*Typha angustifolia*), bulrush (*Scirpus lacustris*). There are also *Jungus gerardi*, *Alisma gramineum*, *Tripolium pannonicum*, *Carex melanostachya*, *Beckmannia eruciformis*, and *Elecharis palustris* from reed-reedmace communities. In addition, *Utricularia vulgaris* and *Batrachium trichophyllum* macrophytes may also occur.

In the freshwater lakes of the Korgalzhyn lake system, aquatic plants *Ceratophyllum demersum* and *Potamogeton pectinatus* are found. *Utricularia vulgaris* may interfere with Reed-tailed communities. In the autumn months, the surface of the Lakes is covered with vegetation *Lemna tricola* and *Lemna minor*. Among the Reed communities, there is an aquatic plant *Hydrocharis morsus-ranae*.

In the salting lakes of Korgalzhyn (Yessey, Sultankeldy, Kokay, Asaubalyk), aquatic vegetation is less common than in fresh lakes. In the open parts, *Potamogeton pectinatus* or *Potamogeton perfoliatus* is found. In some years, *Myriophyllum spicatum* is more common. Among the reeds, *Potamogeton macrocarpus*, *Utricularia vulgaris* and green filamentous algae (*Chlorophyta*) can also be found. In lakes that feed on snow water (Saumalkol), there

are a large number of groups of aquatic plants (*Potamogeton*). In Salt Lakes, the aquatic plant *Ruppia maritima* and the algae *Cladophora* are found.

In the lakes Sholak, Yessey, Sultankeldy, there are more diatomic algae (*Bacillariophyta*) in the species composition of periphiton. Green algae (*Chlorophyta*) and cyanobacteria (*Cyanobacteria*) are less common, but their biomass increases on hot summer days. Beta-Alpha mesasaprobic algae are more common, oligosaprobic algae are less common. In Sultankeldy Lake, euglene algae are found depending on some seasons. The most common relatives of diatomaceous algae include relatives of *Nitzschia*, *Navicula*, *Cymbella*, *Diatoma*. From green algae, there are relatives of *Scenedesmus*, *Pediastrum*.

In Lake Kokay, communities with minimal diversity occur. Periphiton algae species are limited to 9-20 species in each year. The vast majority are diatomic algae.

As a result, the coastal vegetation of Korgalzhyn reservoirs is covered with Reed, clump communities, from aquatic vegetation there are often relatives of *Potamogeton*, *Utricularia*. The species diversity of periphiton algae is dominated by diatomic algae (*Bacillariophyta*).

INFLUENCE OF VERTICAL LOAD ON THE HORIZONTAL BEARING CAPACITY OF A PILE, TAKING SOIL SOAKING AND EARTHQUAKE INTO ACCOUNT

Nyamdorj, S.

Mongolian State University of Science and Technology. Ulaanbaatar. Mongolia.

Dashjamts, D.

Mongolian State University of Science and Technology. Ulaanbaatar. Mongolia.

Keywords: boundary load, friction force, displacement, calculation formula, correlation graph.

Introduction. When analyzing the results of full-scale field tests of a pile foundation, a difficult problem is to determine the regularity of the influence of a vertical load on the horizontal ultimate bearing capacity of a pile. In the practice of calculating the design of a pile foundation, the mechanism of the interdependence of horizontal and vertical loads is not taken into account, it is calculated according to independent individual horizontal and vertical reactions of soil resistance of the foundation of buildings and structures. Research on this topic has been carried out in a limited amount, despite the fact that the results of which are often inconsistent and with significant discrepancies, and also experts in the field of pile foundation construction also reason differently and put forward different assumptions. In the conclusions of the research papers, the mechanism of the influence of vertical force on the horizontal bearing capacity is not defined, most of the studies were carried out in laboratory flumes in sandy soils using model tensor piles on the actions of horizontal and vertical loads.

Experimental-Theoretical justification. As part of our study, we studied and cited works on the original topics of the following researchers, such as Abdel-Rahman, K., Achmus, M. (2006), Achmus, M., Thieken, K. (2010), Grigoryan A.A. (2010), Byrne, B., McAdam, R., Burd, H., Houslyby, G., et al. (2015), Lee, J., Prezzi, M., Salgado, R. (2011), Mangushev, R.A. (2018), Gotman, A.L. (2007), Bakholdin, B.V., Trupanova, E.V. (2010), Kirzhner, F., Rosenhouse, G. (2001), Terzaghi, K. (1955), Zhukov, N.V., Balov, I.L. (1978), Bykov, V.I. (1978), Achmus, M., Thieken, K. (2010), Kudryashov, V. P. (1981), Valsangkar, A., Rao, N. K., Basudhar, P. (1973), Qiang Li, Luke J. Prendergast, Amin Askarinejad and Ken Gavin. (2020), Shakarji, Yu. (1964), Droshkevich, N.M. (1999), Znamensky, V.V. (2002), Lu, W., Zhang, G. (2018), Nyamdorj, S., Dashzhamts, D., Mangushev, R.A. (2021), Chatterjee, K., Choudhury, D. (2015). In the works of these researchers, experimental and theoretical substantiations of the work of a pile and a pile foundation under the action of horizontal and vertical forces are presented, including the mechanism of the effect of vertical load on the horizontal bearing capacity of piles.

Research methods and materials. In order to identify the effect of vertical load on the horizontal bearing of bored piles with a length of 8.0 m and a diameter of 0.6 m, in subsiding loess-like soil with natural moisture and water-saturated state, taking into account earthquake activity and the regional features of soil conditions in Mongolia, we performed a field test and analytical calculation, numerical analysis (Nyamdorj S., Dashzhamts D., Mangushev R.A. 2021).

Analysis of Calculation results. Comparing the results of analytical and numerical studies, it is established that the horizontal bearing capacity of a pile in subsiding soils with natural moisture and under the condition of a 7 point earthquake under the action of vertical loads of 30.0 tons by 21%, 45.0 tons by 30% and 60.0 tons by 45% increase, with water-saturated humidity under the action of vertical loads of 30.0 tons by 29%, 45.0 tons by 43% and 60.0

tons by 59%. These results are comparable with the results of analytical calculation and numerical analysis by Chatterjee, K., Choudhury, D. (2015).

Conclusions. In the future, based on the results of numerous field and laboratory tests, analytical calculations and numerical analyzes, taking into account the mechanism of changes in physical and mechanical properties during the soaking of subsiding soil of the base, earthquakes and the regularity of the interdependence of horizontal and vertical loads, it is possible to identify certain resources of the calculated bearing capacity of the pile foundation. And also, depending on the degree of complexity of the engineering and geological conditions of the construction site and the degree of responsibility of the buildings and structures under construction, it may be possible to introduce coefficients equal to 1.0-1.2 into the calculation formula to take into account the bearing capacity of the pile.

**TO STUDY THE COMPOSITION AND PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL COVER IN
THE STUDY AREAS OF THE ALMATY REGION**

Kozybaeva F.E.

Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor, Chief Researcher, Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry named for U.U.Uspanov, Almaty

Beiseyeva G.B.

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Chief Researcher, Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry named for U.U.Uspanov, Almaty

Saparov G.A.

Candidate of Agricultural Sciences, Head of the Department of Soil Ecology, Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry named for U.U.Uspanov, Almaty

Toktar M.

PhD Doctor, researcher, Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry named for U.U.Uspanov, Almaty

Azhikina N.Zh.

researcher, Kazakh Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry named for U.U.Uspanov, Almaty

In the process of studying the soil cover of the Almaty region, common soil and ecological violations of the soil cover were identified, i.e. anthropogenic, pasture digression, degradation, landslides and erosion processes. On steep mountain slopes, loose areas with cliffs and rocky outcrops predominate. Erosion processes develop on the slopes of the studied objects, scree forms, in places - landslides. At the studied objects: intensive grazing of large, small cattle, sheep and horses is carried out; vegetation cover is disturbed, in some places vegetation is completely destroyed, the surface horizons of soils are destroyed; there are many man-made, terraced pasture trails; tourists moving directly down or up the slope on foot or on land have a more destructive effect on the soil; an abandoned apple orchard with a large number of fallen tree species has been discovered. There are deeply leached chernozems, low-power chernozems, dark chestnut poorly developed on gravelly eluvium-deluvium of dense rocks, gray-brown desert poorly developed on pebbly and gravelly-pebble eluvium and proluvium, floodplain meadow, desert sands slightly humus carbonate ridge-bumpy soils. The determination of field humidity coincides with the morphogenetic description of soil sections in the conditions of field research. The bulk mass in the upper horizons shows soil compaction with a decrease in porosity, primarily interaggregate, and deterioration of the water-air regime. According to the granulometric composition of the soil of the studied object, they belong to light, medium and heavy loamy and sandy. Analytical data show that the humus content in the upper horizons of the studied soils ranges from 0.8 to 9.12%. According to the classification of soils by humus content, the soils of the studied area are medium and high humus. The CO₂ content in the soil ranges from 0.2-12.4%. Its high content in the soil (> 3%) has a negative effect on seeds, inhibits the development of plants. According to the obtained data, the soils of the object under study can be attributed according to the existing gradations from weak to provide with mobile forms of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. The soils of the object of study on the scale are slightly acidic, slightly alkaline, alkaline, pH is 6-8,9. The Ca content ranges from 2 - 25.3 mg-eq, i.e. 62.3-87.6%. The magnesium content ranges from 0.5 -5.45 mg-eq, i.e. from 3.6-30.2%. Saturation of the absorbing complex with calcium, provides plants with a favorable, close to neutral reaction of the soil, protects its absorbing complex from destruction, promotes aggregation of the soil and anchoring of humus in it.

**MODERN TRENDS IN FIELD SEISMIC ACQUISITION AND ACQUIRED DATA
PROCESSING METHODS**

Katrenov Zhanibek

Kazakh National Research Technical University named after K. I. Satpayev, Kazakhstan

Abetov Auez

Kazakh National Research Technical University named after K. I. Satpayev, Kazakhstan

Field seismic records are often incomplete due to missing data. Recovery of missing seismic data is necessary for the processing and interpretation of seismic data. As an effective solution to this problem, the paper considers reflection seismic methods for acquisition and processing based on Compressive seismic acquisition (CSA), compressive seismic reconstruction (CSR) and simultaneous source shooting (blended). The capabilities and geological problems that can be solved by each of the above-mentioned methods are considered separately, as well as in the case of their complex application. The factual basis of the conducted research was made up of a wide range of scientific publications, including the field experimental results of the application of these methods.

The method of CSA is based on the principle of compressive sensing (CS), allows to carry out seismic survey with irregular indexing (arrangement of receiver and shot points) and is applicable to any geometry and design of survey. The fundamental concept behind CS is non-uniformly sampling the seismic data to let normally coherent aliased energy become incoherently sampled while maintaining the coherent sampling of seismic signal.

The method of reconstructing seismic data from purposely skipped or missing traces is based on the extension to POCS (Projection Onto Convex Sets) interpolation method. The main idea of this approach differs significantly from many previous interpolation methods, since it considers the reconstruction of seismic data as a task of obtaining high-resolution images in "computer vision" and directly indicates the hidden relationship between incomplete and complete seismic data, even with irregular indexing, according to a number of specific criteria and calculation algorithms. Thus, compressive reconstruction of seismic data helps to convert incomplete input seismic data into complete ones.

With the simultaneous source shooting method several sources of seismic energy located at various shot points get triggered one after another within few seconds allowing to save enormous time resources by eliminating the wait time between source recordings.

All three methods described in this paper can significantly optimize the execution of field seismic surveys while providing high image quality even with a smaller number of receiver stations for elastic vibrations and overlapping signal from various source points. Given the significant advantages of these methods, they can be considered as next generation reflection seismic technologies for operational effectiveness and high-resolution seismic recording.

Physics & Mathematics

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- *Mathematical Physics*
- *Nonlinear Science*
- *Optics & Photonics*
- *Physics & Mathematics (general)*
- *Plasma & Fusion*
- *Probability & Statistics with Applications*
- *Pure & Applied Mathematics*
- *Quantum Mechanics*
- *Spectroscopy & Molecular Physics*
- *Thermal Sciences*

THE EFFECT OF ELECTRON RADIATION ON A LINEAR POLYMER AND COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Tlebaev Kairat Beishenovich

Doctor of physical and mathematical sciences, professor, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University

Kadyrova Ademau Nurlanovna

2nd year Master student of the Department of Physics, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University

Zhanabay Yernar Zhumagalievich

2nd year Master student of the Department of Physics, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University

Data on the effect of ionizing radiation on the thermal characteristics of polymer materials and composites are of particular interest. The study of the effects of ionizing radiation on thermal properties can provide valuable information about the relationship between its structure and properties. However, despite the importance of information on the effect of radiation exposure on the thermal characteristics of polymers and composites, experimental data in this area is very few. This paper presents the results of studies of the effect of electron radiation on the heat capacity of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and composites (getinax, fiberglass) in the temperature range of 80-330 K. To study the effect of electron irradiation on the heat capacities of PTFE, getinax and fiberglass, we irradiated the samples with electrons up to doses of 0.4, 1 and 2 MGy. The samples were irradiated in the air. The heat capacity measurements were carried out at the experimental installation TAU-5 in the temperature range of 80-330 K. The experimental temperature dependences of the heat capacity of PTFE, getinax and fiberglass were obtained between 80-330 K at radiation doses of 0.4; 1 and 2 MGy. The analysis of the heat capacity of irradiated PTFE showed the linear increase with increasing temperature up to 293 K. At 293 and 303 K, the heat capacity increases sharply, which is due to phase transitions. As the temperature increases, the heat capacity decreases. Irradiation with doses of 0.04 and 1 MGy leads to a decrease in heat capacity, and at a dose of 2 MGy increases. The linear dependence of the heat capacity and its decrease at low doses is explained by the ratio of crystalline and amorphous phases, and the increase at doses above 1 MGy can be explained by reducing crystallinity and increasing the number of internal degrees of freedom. At doses of 0.04 and 1 MGy phase transitions on the curves of temperature dependences of the heat capacity of irradiated PTFE are shifted by 1 and 13 K respectively to the low temperature region, which is because of a decrease in the length of the PTFE chain. The heat capacity of the studied composites increases linearly with increasing temperature. With an increase in the radiation dose, the heat capacity increases. When electronic irradiation acts on composite materials, reversible and irreversible radiation changes occur in them. The irreversible changes in the heat capacity of composites are because of structural transformations – processes of radiation crosslinking or destruction.

STUDY A FRACTIONALLY LOADED HEAT EQUATION WITH A LOAD AS A RIEMANN-LIOUVILLE DERIVATIVE

Izhanova Kamila Alibekovna

Buketov Karaganda University, (Karaganda city, Kazakhstan)

Kosmakova Minzilya Timerbayevna

Buketov Karaganda University, (Karaganda city, Kazakhstan)

We study the fractionally loaded heat equation with a load as a Riemann-Liouville derivative with respect to the time variable. The study of set boundary value problem is concluded with obtaining the integral equation. Also, we checked the limit cases for the fractional order derivative in the heat equation of BVP. It could be seen that the order of the fractional derivative is crucial in stating the existence and uniqueness of solutions.

The differential theory and fractional integration have been developing thanks to their application in different fields of science. Noticeably, the fractional derivative study has been done actively in previous decades. The interest in its study develops to grow too now [3-6]. Application of fractional derivatives, especially of Riemann-Liouville type, has been used in physics problems which involve impulses. This paper is about a boundary value problem of a heat equation with the fractional load. The load is a Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of the first order. Using the general solution and manipulating through the solution the original problem has been reduced to a Volterra integral equation of a second kind with a kernel of degenerated hypergeometric Tricomi function. Later the limiting cases in the $[0,1]$ interval it was proven that solution in the boundary values correspond to the kernel of the function.

To sum up, kernel of the integral equation has a weak singularity. Consequently, to find an unique solution to the equation in the class of continuous functions, it is possible to apply method of successive approximations. Natural classes of functions are well-posed homogenous boundary value problems.

The use of fractional derivatives can be applied in solving applied physics, chemistry, finance, and other problems. For example, classical theorem of Nutting and Newton for describing a material under the external force can be further modeled with fractional load explaining the viscoelastic metals. The higher the order of the fractional derivative, the more challenging equation becomes.

REACTION RATE OF RADIATIVE $n^8\text{Li}$ CAPTURE IN THE RANGE FROM 0.01 TO $10 T_9$

Dubovichenko Sergey Borisovich

Dr. of Phys. and Math. Sciences, Professor, Fesenkov Astrophysical Institute

Yeleusheva Badigul Maratovna

PhD student, Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi

Burkova Natalya Aleksandrovna

Dr. of Phys. and Math. Sciences, Professor, Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi

Within the framework of the modified potential cluster model with forbidden states based on $E1$ and $M1$ transitions, the total cross sections are calculated for capture to the ground state of the ^9Li nucleus in the $n^8\text{Li}$ channel in the energy range from 10 meV to 5 MeV, which includes a resonance at 0.232 MeV (c.m.) in the $P_{5/2}$ wave and a possible resonance in the $P_{3/2}$ wave at 1.32 MeV. The $M1$ and $E1$ transitions to the 1st excited state of ^9Li at the same energies are also taken into account. The influence of the value of the asymptotic constant on the behaviour of the total capture cross sections is studied. Further, based on the obtained cross sections, the reaction rate calculated in the temperature range from 0.01 to $10 T_9$. The reaction rate approximated by a simple analytical expression.

Figure 1. - The reaction rate of neutron capture on ^8Li nucleus.

The total cross sections for radiative capture at energies in the range from 10 meV to 5 MeV are obtained that generally agree with the results of experimental measurements. The reaction rate was calculated and a simple form of its approximation are proposed. The dependence of the rate on the value of asymptotic constant of ground state and 1st ES has been studied, which shows an almost two times difference in the results for different values of asymptotic constant. Two reaction rate results shown by the red continuous curve and the red double-dashed line, seem to determine the possible range of rates for this reaction. Another

Young diagram for the ${}^8\text{Li}$ nucleus used in work, which follows from our results obtained in previous work [1]. According to the new classification of Young diagrams, interaction potentials of particles in all states and partial scattering waves are obtained. Taking into account two additional transitions from $P_{1/2}$ and $P_{3/2}$ scattering waves [2]. A simple form of analytical parametrization for the reaction rate is proposed. In previous work [2], the parametrization of the reaction rate was not performed at all. An interval of reaction rates was obtained at $T_9 = 1$ from 5740 to 11000, which depends on the value of asymptotic constant. An interval equal to 5900 obtained in previous work without taking into account the resonance at 232 keV. Taking into account the first resonance at 232 keV, the reaction rates obtained in the range from 0.01 to $10 T_9$. In earlier data [2], the rate was calculated only up to $2 T_9$ and the resonance effect was not taken into account. As a result, it can be seen that the modified potential cluster model is quite capable of leading to results for total cross sections and reaction rates that generally describe the existing experiment.

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KAZAKHSTAN: IMPROVING A LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR A CORPORATE STRUCTURE

Farkhad Karagussov

doctor of Law, professor at Caspian University (Almaty, Kazakhstan), associate member of the International Academy of Comparative Law (IACL)

Kazakh legislation adopted a classic dualistic model of corporate structure. Such a structure is prescribed for formation in limited liability partnerships (LLPs). Such regulation of the corporate structure of an LLP is mandatory. However, for years there have been LLPs whose corporate structure does not comply (in fact, violates) that legal requirements. Although not a common practice, such cases are puzzling, since both in accordance with the best practices of corporate governance and in accordance with Kazakhstani legislation, the responsibility for managing a company, observing rights of its creditors and other stakeholders lies entirely with the company's bodies. At the same time, depending on a corporate structure of the company, the responsibility for observing the rights and interests of stakeholders is distributed differently.

The clarity of the corporate structure allows investors to understand who has the right to make corporate decisions in the company, to represent it and interact with them. Such a clear understanding creates appropriate conditions for investors to make an informed decision on investing their funds in the company's capital or providing it with debt financing.

According to best international practice and Kazakhstani legislation, a proper corporate structure is one of the key elements of an effective corporate governance system. The objectivity of formation of a corporate structure leads to the imperativeness of regulating acceptable models of a corporate structure, including the situation when a national law introduces the modern approach of mixed regulation. This largely determines the level and quality of legal guarantees, as well as a degree of protection of rights of members of commercial corporations, the companies' creditors, investors and other stakeholders.

Resistance to regulate the legal status of companies by mandatory provisions of national legislation will cause a return to the practice of self-regulation, which in developed jurisdictions has long been recognized not only as ineffective, but also harmful. The imperative nature of regulating the corporate structure does not allow any contractual regulation of these matters by members (shareholders) of a company. The corporate structure prescribed in the law cannot be changed by a contract between the members (shareholders).

Although the corporate law presupposes and ensures coordination of the will of participants in corporate relations, traditionally contractual arrangements within the framework of these relations has a very specific expression and, therefore, a very limited application. Corporate law offers other mechanisms and tools for coordinating wills, i.e. the one within the framework of the constituent assembly and the general meeting of members of corporations, as well as within the framework of decision-making by collegiate bodies of the company. It also implies accountability, appropriate execution of corporate decisions, compliance with the rules established by the company's bodies^ i.e. something that does not exist in traditional contractual relationships. The very dynamics of corporate relations and contractual relations fundamentally differ from each other, and does not allow their interchangeability.

In this regard, modernization of the corporate legislation of Kazakhstan should start not with fragmentary changes, but peculiarities of our legal system (as the law of the Civil Code) shall be taken into account. Particularly, it should be legislatively recognized that, among other types of legal relations, civil legislation specifically regulates corporate relations.

In addition, the list of grounds for the emergence, change and termination of civil rights and obligations shall be correspondingly expanded in the Civil Code. Besides, the existing classifications of legal entities and their organizational and legal forms shall be changed, as well as a number of other changes and additions at the level of the existing Civil Code shall be introduced.

BAENGYEONG ISLAND - REGIONAL SECURITY DILEMMA

Barlykbayeva Madina

4th year student of the Department of Oriental Studies,
Faculty of International Relations, L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Relevance of the topic. Out of current International Relations problems related to Korea such as unification, Korean- Northeast Asian countries relations, issues of The Law of the Sea contain all of the main points of all Korean International Affair issues. When discussing the peace process on the Korean Peninsula, as a rule, in a territorial and geopolitical context, more attention is on to the potential threat to the peninsula's land relations, i.e. the situation of Panmunjom on the 38th parallel and the nuclear weapons testing by the North. However, from a geographical point of view, the territory of South Korea consists of the southern part of the Korean Peninsula, Jeju and more than 3000 small islands. In addition, the island, known by the names Dokdo (독도) and Takeshima (竹島), is also considered the territory of the Republic of Korea under international law (1954), which is in international subjects related to Korea.

However, there are not many works where the protection of island territories included in the Korean Peninsula following international maritime law and the UN Convention on Maritime law combining these issues, examined separately in the international arena and the role of these islands in international relations. The main reason for this is the presence of a military base protected by the combined American and Korean troops and ordinary people could not enter those areas.

This thesis is devoted to maritime issues on the Korean Peninsula and studies how international law affects peace and conflict in the Northeast Asian region. From the current problems of international relations related to Korea, such as Korea's relations with the countries of Northeast Asia, the unification of the two Koreas, the issues of maritime law cover the main subjects of all Korean international problems. The affairs between other Northeastern Asia countries and Korea consociates by marine: Korea is encircled by water on its three sides, the West Sea on the west, East Sea on the east and Korean Strait on the south side; Baengnyeong and Ulleung Islands have been crucial areas for economic, military and strategic perspectives. Thus, issues related to maritime regions, military, economy and environmental dilemmas are related directly to security and peace in the Korean Peninsula and the Northeast Asian region, and writing work on this topic is an eminent direction in international affairs.

The object of the study is the South Korean island of Baengnyeong.

The subject of the study is the island's characteristic features, history, role and current state in international relations.

Purpose of the work. Identify and evaluate the strategic position of Baengnyeong Island in the North-East Asian region, its role in influencing security and peace, its main features and potential threats or, conversely, opportunities that may arise in the future.

For achieving the purpose of the work, **the following tasks are stipulate:**

- ❖ Differentiation of the historical development of Baengnyeong island;
- ❖ Study of the strategic and political context of Baengnyeong island;
- ❖ Identification of the main stages of development of maritime law and features of Baengnyeong Island and Incheon Islands;
- ❖ Consideration of the consequences, natural, human and financial losses caused by the North Korean attack of 2010 and the place of the incident in the international arena;

- ❖ Analysis and differentiation of the problem of islands in relations between the DPRK and the ROK;
- ❖ Examine the view on the South Korean islands in international relations and international law;
- ❖ Compare the differences and features of news related to the Korean islands in foreign media.

THE ROLE OF DISCOURSE IN THE FORMATION OF THE SUBJECT OF COGNITION

Ismayilova Aybaniz Arif

Lecturer, Orcid ID:0000-0001-9931-9254, (Odlar Yurdu University)

Keywords: discursive activity, cognitive ability, implicit expression

As a system of special interpretation of knowledge discourse is organized according to a single anthropocentric coordinate - the subject of cognition. In discourse, the subject of cognition acts as a subject of discursive activity [speaking / writing], perceiving a fragment of real reality in relation to the individual system of knowledge. The subject of discursive activity uses existing knowledge when interpreting the world, uses various mental operations, and the discourse refers to a special cognitive ability that allows the interaction of events and their participants as a fragment of reality. This is reflected in its two cognitive abilities - the ability to act as a subject of discursive knowledge and the subject of discursive organization of knowledge. These two cognitive abilities allow discourse to be organized as a complex and holistic knowledge format. Discourse, as a format of knowledge, represents their special organization, that is, it records a certain cognitive model of the organization of the world. This model is based on the interpretive activity of the subject of discursive activity, in which the typical content and structural organization of the discourse is carried out.

Subjective representation of knowledge about the world is achieved by including a fragment of reality in the discourse, distinguishing the subject as a special participant due to the attitude of that fragment and knowledge and the source of ideas about it and other discourse participants. The enumerated abilities of the subject of discursive knowledge find their implicit expression in language. In its turn, the ability to act as a subject of discursive organization of knowledge is the ability of the subject to select and express relevant knowledge at that moment of communication. This ability allows the subject to create a discourse on the individual's perception and understanding of the situation.

Thus, the discourse, which in itself represents a complex organized space of mental contact with the surrounding reality, acts as a special process and the result of its perception. The emergence of discourse is conditioned by complex processes of conceptualization and categorization, within which a wide range of knowledge of discourse participants is included and activated. As a result of operations with knowledge in different ways, the discourse is formed as a complex mental-linguistic representation of a separate fragment of reality.

The organization of knowledge in the discourse by the subjects of discourse activity represents the process of dynamic interaction of different contexts. The discourse distinguishes two main types of context, internal and external. Under the internal context of discourse is its appeal to the cognitive systems of the subjects of discursive activity.

According to A.Y. Mammadov, who interprets the discourse as a result of the subject's cognitive processes, "*The reasons for the formation of discourse, its formation and eventual success depend on the internal context of the participants in the discourse*" [14, p. 47]. In another work, the author writes about the internal context: "*The internal context is the knowledge associated with a person's individual knowledge of the world. The internal context is knowledge about knowledge. The subjectivity of discourse, and political discourse in general, is based on the internal context*" [15, p. 30].

This context accumulates all the knowledge of the subjects of discursive activity. At the internal level of discourse, the knowledge of discourse participants is statically preserved in their various presentation structures (concepts, frames, scenarios, cognitive schemes). The structure of the internal context is very diverse and covers different blocks of knowledge as a

result of understanding the world. Such blocks of thought include knowledge of the world, cognitive regulators, knowledge of language, and knowledge of a specific communication situation.

It should be noted that such knowledge is represented in the knowledge of both non-linguistic objects and the realities of the surrounding reality and the inner world of man. Cognitive regulators can be viewed as psychologically conditioned knowledge. The inclusion of this type of knowledge in the act of communication (discourse) is the result of the intensive conditioning of discursive activity. Examples of knowledge regulators are the subject's beliefs, desires, and intentions. T.A. van Dyke distinguishes "*knowledge, beliefs, needs, privileges, dreams, attitudes, feelings and emotions in the structure of the internal context*" [71, p. 12].

One of the ideas repeatedly voiced in cognitive linguistics is that collective knowledge is reinforced in the systematic meanings of language units, the language system, unlike the "individual conceptual system" that represents the subject's individual knowledge in discourse, represents the collective knowledge known as the "objective conceptual system". In other words, each natural language represents a specific way of organizing [conceptualizing] and understanding the world. It is language that preserves collective knowledge. As N.N. Boldirev noted, "*If the process of perception of the world is always individual and based on the experience of its own practical, mental or verbal interaction with reality, verbal communication requires a certain level of standardization of knowledge, the participants of the act of communication must have a certain level of knowledge as members of cultural, national, territorial, social, professional and other associations*" [37, p. 26].

It is known that collective knowledge, which is represented in language and has a certain shape in terms of volume, content and interpretation, is the essence of individual knowledge of the world. Since cognition is always individual, then the individuality of knowledge is reflected in a person's level of mastery of quantitative and content indicators of collective knowledge in his individual assessment and interpretation.

Knowledge of the situation of communication (situation) and the type of discourse represents the mental structure formed in the mind of the subject. This knowledge, as noted by M.L. Makarov, "*is directly related to the specific communication situation, specific discourse, style of discourse, subject and register of communication*" [113, p. 96]. Knowledge of the communication situation and discourse ensures the appropriate communicative behavior of the subject of discursive activity. In other words, "*subjects understand language expressions only if they interpret the contexts in which those expressions occur*" [211, p. 73]. Thus, the peculiarity of this type of knowledge is that the organization of the discourse is possible only if this knowledge is part of the inner world of the participants in the discourse, that is, taking into account the fact that each subject of discursive activity has its own mental representation.

Discourse is a form of social behavior that contributes to the formation of the social world and thus serves to maintain and protect social relations. Discourse shapes the social world with the help of meanings. Taking into account that language is changeable, meaning cannot be permanent at all. This leads to the fact that no discourse is closed and exhaustive, in fact, the discourse is constantly changing in the process of interaction with other discourses. Thus, language is not a channel for the transmission of information about everyday events, facts and human behavior, but a mechanism for generating and creating the social world. This includes both social identity and social relations. In other words, changes in discourse are a way of changing the social world.

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**DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION OF THE
REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN**

Toleubekova Bakhitzhan

Doctor of Law, Professor, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Kazakhstan

Khvedelidze Teimuraz Bichikoevich

Candidate of Law Sciences, Associate Professor, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Kazakhstan

Sailibaeva Zhanel

Candidate of Law Sciences, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Kazakhstan

Применение цифровых технологий в системе высшего образования Республики Казахстан условно можно разделить на три периода. Первый период определяется моментом вступления Казахстана в Болонский процесс организации системы высшего образования и заканчивается введением в стране чрезвычайного положения, связанного с пандемией коронавируса. Он исчисляется с 2007 года по февраль 2019 года. Второй период охватывает время нахождения вузовского образования в условиях пандемии коронавируса: с марта 2019 года по февраль 2022 года. Третий период мы связываем с моментом снятия карантинных ограничений и переходом на традиционный режим образовательного процесса, продолжающийся по настоящее время.

Первый период характеризуется тенденциями роста применения информационно-коммуникационных технологий (далее – ИКТ): 1) начальное освоение разрешительных способностей ИКТ, их адаптация к вузовским условиям; 2) реализация мер, обеспечивающих соответствие параметрам Болонского процесса путем (применение интерактивной доски, электронных журналов учета посещаемости занятий, подготовка и издание электронных версий учебно-методических комплексов дисциплин, создание электронных библиотек и т.д.); 3) приобретение профессорско-преподавательским составом навыков пользования компьютерными технологиями. Особенности этого периода: планомерное и последовательное вхождение в сферу компьютерных технологий, сочетание традиционных и новых технологий организации учебного процесса и контроля остаточных знаний, избирательный подход к видам цифровых технологий, проработка вопросов информационной безопасности.

Второй период в силу неординарности обстоятельств, обусловивших срочность перехода на дистанционное обучение, характеризуется следующими особенностями: 1) применение цифровых технологий без адаптации к специфике специальности; 2) цифровизация всех видов занятий без учета совместимости имеющихся технологий с особенностями учебной дисциплины; 3) спешное наращивание физических объемов применяемых ИКТ; 4) отсутствие эффективных методик применения цифровых технологий в образовании; 5) большое количество сбоев в сетях из-за сильных перегрузок с последующим снижением качества передачи и приема образовательной информации; 6) крайне низкий уровень обратной связи; 7) слабый уровень ведомственной регламентации методики применения цифровых технологий, отсутствие мер обеспечения информационной безопасности. В результате – снижение качества образования, одновременный рост манипулирования цифровыми технологиями, сопряженного с коррупционными правонарушениями.

Начало третьего периода: основные субъекты образовательной деятельности (обучаемый и преподаватель) с удовлетворением восприняли возвращение к традиционным технологиям обучения в режиме «of line». Пройденные уроки тотальной цифровизации сферы высшего образования будут проанализированы и подвергнуты

объективной оценке на предмет определения параметров разумного сочетания традиционной и цифровой методик вузовского образования.

THE PROBLEM OF STUDY EUPHEMIZATION OF LEXICAL UNITS IN ECOLOGICAL DISCOURSE

Kuanyshbayeva Arailym Nurgazievna

PhD student, Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Makhpirov Velinur Uigurovich

Doctor of Science, Professor, Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Problems of ecology is not only actual nowadays, but the future of humanity depends on the rational and timely solutions of such problems. The ecological situation is on the agenda of many countries. Therefore, the study of language material related to ecological discourse is very popular in the modern linguistics. Texts of ecological issues have special function and unite text structure of different genres: scientific, publicist, art and official. They discuss such issues like climate change on planet, consequences of natural and techno genic disaster, consumer attitude to the nature and its resources from human side, the emergence of an epidemic due to human activity.

Regardless of characteristic and genre of texts of ecological discourse, we need to focus attention of recipient on the necessity to protect nature, adherence to the norms of environmental competent behavior. Studies carried out on the material of English language texts on environmental topics show that the overwhelming majority of lexical units are represented by extensive group of neologisms. On the one hand, we are talking about proper neologisms and semantic rethinks denoting new concept and realities that have appeared in the field of ecology. On the other hand, as the results of the conducted research show, this lexical group is represented, first, by euphemisms, lexical units that give a new, more appropriate name to the traditional realities that already have their own name. Their usage is associated with the need to improve the linguistic mechanism because of the formation of a new ecological consciousness, which at the present historical stage begins to include a moral component and is opposed to traditional ideas.

A euphemism in linguistics mean “replacing any illegal or undesirable word or expression with more correct one in order to avoid the direct name of everything that can cause negative feelings, both in the speaker and in the recipient/interlocutor , as well as with the aim of masking certain facts of reality”. L.V. Porakhnitskaya defines euphemism as “a word or phrase used instead of another word or phrase, which for moral, ethical, aesthetic, religious and other reasons seem inappropriate in this context”. Thus, euphemisms act as special synonyms used instead of words that people deliberately avoid. Euphemisms, as words used by a speaker to replace unwanted names, arise in a language for a number of pragmatic and extralinguistic reasons. From a pragmatic point of view, there are two main goals of communication that determine the euphemization of speech:

1. Desire to avoid communicative conflicts
2. Camouflage the essence of the matter

In the latter case the speaker, referring to some subject can use such linguistic means that allow him to hide the real subject of presentation. In modern English – speaking environmental discourse, the emergence of euphemisms is due to the following pragmatic reasons:

1. Desire to conceal some of the impartial aspects or phenomena of reality, which are usually kept silent in society. For example, the well-known euphemism “biosolids” is used instead of human waste.

2. Desire to hide the real scale of pollution, harm, distract from the impending danger. Examples include ozone nonattainment area instead of a locality with high air pollution level, routine exceedances instead of regular violation level, research whaling instead of a study in terms of activity of hunting whales.

As noted E.V. Ivanova, the language of ecological discourse is characterized by the presence of lexical units with a vague, abstract meaning, including euphemisms and hide much more than it explains. To describe the phenomenon “greenspeak” (Eco speak) was created – a language that hide the true scale of environmental problems. Euphemistic units in such cases are formed by generalization or paraphrasing by using lexical unit of a broader general meaning adapted to a specific context, paraphrasing in order to remove the emphasis on one or another aspect of meaning, veiling unnecessary information.

In this case, the very concept of euphemism can be interpreted in different ways by different researchers. Therefore, M.V. Basinskaya, a large number of whose works are devoted to research within the framework of environmental linguistics, speaking about the lexical and semantic features of environmental discourse, along with euphemisms, distinguishes a separate group of lexical units with “indefinite semantics”. These include, for example, such units as “disposal” or “sustainable”. Having quite wide combinable possibilities in this type of discourse, they tend to expand their meaning and are not easy to perceive and understand in a specific context. This characterizes the entire ecological discourse as a whole – a rich and at the same time, confusing terminology has developed in ecological discourse. The process of interpreting some lexical units is so complicated that it requires a wide context of use or additional explanations.

However, a stable combination with such lexeme can become quite popular in the language of discourse, naming a phenomenon that is relevant and important for understanding. A number of scholars correlate such lexical combinations also with the sphere of euphemisms, where the essence of euphemization is to use the term in order to take into account the stylistic features of an ecological scientific text – abstractness and generalization. So, for example, the combination of sustainable development, translated most often, but not quite exactly, as “sustainable development”, is quite common in different types of environmental contexts: Sustainable development goals, sustainable development concepts, sustainable development conference, etc. Despite the vagueness of the adjective sustainable (sustainable, stable, environmentally-friendly, taking into accounts the needs of the future generalization” – in its use in environmental discourse) the phrase appeals to an already fully formed conceptual concept within the framework of discourse

The use of this kind of vocabulary in environmental texts, on the one hand, makes their language not always easily accessible for perception, on the other hand, passing from text to text; such units become kind of codes, keys to understand the essence of the processes occurring as in modern society and in modern language. The so-called “linguistic creativity” within the framework of ecological discourse, which is realized in the process of euphemization of vocabulary, the emergence of neologisms and the expansion of meanings, is designed to coordinate the ways of human perception of global environmental problems.

THE CRISIS IN AFGHANISTAN AND THE THREAT OF CENTRAL ASIA

V.Iztaeva

Candidate of Political Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Modern History of Kazakhstan and worldview disciplines, Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and World Languages.

Abstract. The article analyzes the current political situation in Afghanistan, the rise of the Taliban, the emergence of ISIS in Afghanistan and the activation of al-Qaeda, the mass infiltration of ISIS-linked militants into Afghanistan. The article discusses the ideological basis of the extremist organization of the Taliban. The analysis shows that the Taliban ideology is based on the fundamentalist theories of the Deobandi school and the radical views of the Tablighi Jamaat movement.

Keywords: Taliban, Mujahideen, Islam, Pashtun, Batken war, cross-border criminal groups, Khorosan factor, Pashtunwali, regional security, conflict resolution, international terrorism, international relations.

The introduction justifies the choice of the topic, its relevance and novelty, the scientific and practical significance of the study, sets out the goals and objectives, defines the methodological foundations of the work, and analyzes the degree of development of the topic. Over the past four decades, Afghanistan has been in the spotlight of the world's leading media outlets. As the situation in this country escalates, the attention of the world's leading publications has shifted to this country. Events in Afghanistan are so rapid and dramatic that the focus is on the country dimension of the Afghan problem – the transfer of power, the fate of refugees, the beginning of political and humanitarian crises, and the likelihood of civil war. However, we must not forget that the situation in Afghanistan has a broader regional and global significance.

The stages of the study in our article cover the history of the creation of the Taliban and the scale of the seizure of Afghanistan and its rise to power as an organization. Our article used various scientific analysis, description, comparison, forecasting, comparative-historical method system and historical approach, content analysis, which allowed us to analyze in detail the most important processes and trends in the modern history of the situation in Afghanistan.

Such issues will become the main ones in the near future, and it is quite possible that the internal situation of Afghans will remain secondary, or it will become a derivative of international topics, which will determine the specifics of the approach to the development of events in Afghanistan. There is an opinion that the main role in the problem of Afghanistan is played by external actors. It is possible that in the near future the Talibs will become not only the main subject of the state, but also independent in their own way.

THE USE OF THE ART TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THE PROFESSIONAL POSITION OF FUTURE PSYCHOLOGIST-TEACHERS

Dinara Kakabayeva

PhD, Department of Social Pedagogy and Self-knowledge L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Gulsara Zhussupbekova

Department of Social and Age Pedagogy Sh. Ualikhanov Kokshetau University

Zhaslan Nakeshev

Department of Pedagogy and Psychology Sh. Ualikhanov Kokshetau University

This article deals with the formation of the professional position of future psychologist teachers of the Republic of Kazakhstan through art technologies. The relevance of this topic is that the intensity of socio-cultural development of the current society of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as the introduction of new processes in the educational space puts forward fundamentally new requirements in the training of teaching staff. In this regard, it is necessary to train educational psychologists who are able to contribute professionally to the implementation of the modern educational process in the development of the entire educational space in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The purpose of this article is to analyze and justify the theoretical aspects of the formation of the professional of future psychologist teachers by means of art technology, as well as determine the conditions of their effective use in the training of qualified specialists. The methodological basis of this study was the provisions of the proactive human role in the transformation of the psychological environment in the process of self-realization; transfer of competent information in the process of continuing education in the world; personality-oriented and socio-cultural approaches, which focus on the formation of pedagogical provisions of psychology on the understanding of personality in the process of artistic creativity, pedagogical meaning of art technology, professional activity, as well as the ideas of socio-pedagogical design. Theoretical analysis of the use of art technology in the educational process of the Republic of Kazakhstan were chosen as the main methods of knowledge. Practical significance of the research on the topic «Formation of professional position of future psychologist teachers by means of art technologies» can be applied in the development of programs and methods of art therapy in the system of professional psychological and pedagogical education in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

REFLECTION ON POSSIBLE «MEDIA LITERACY WARS» ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Tashchenko Anna Iuriivna

Candidate of Sociological Sciences (PhD in Sociology), Assistant Professor at the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

Researchers of social media and fake news are acquainted with different metaphors of war: «likewar» (P. W. Singer, E. T. Brooking), «cognitive wars» and «virtual wars» (G. Pocheptsov), «communication wars» (A. Harus), «information wars» (R. Stengel), etc. There are countless fact-checking initiatives and self-help media literacy toolkits around the world – and it is forgotten that there can be many versions of media literacy, which should not be divided according to the binary principle being common even for critical studies.

In collaboration with Research & Branding Group, in 2020, I researched how Ukrainians usually distinguish between true and false information on social media. We selected 14 criteria for a representative nationwide survey: 7 of them were indicative of individualism in the search for truth, and 7 of them were indicative of collectivism in the same process. At first glance, it seemed that everything was decided in favor of individualism because of one's own intuition being with a wide margin from other alternatives. But the cluster analysis (done through intergroup connection method and Jaccard distance measure) showed that yes, one's own intuition matters for all six types of information consumers found – however, in fact, there were two types of individualists, one mixed type, and three types of collectivists.

It would be correct to assume that the cause of the new social divide is about *whose version* of individualist / collectivist / mixed media literacy is more viable / effective / honest / dangerous, etc. And it is not only about accepting or rejecting something like «the mom test» (R. Fitzpatrick) or its alternatives regarding old & new media informing. The second part of my research in collaboration with the R&BG was the identification of social media users' types, when in the list of social media there were «VKontakte» and «Odnoklassniki» accused of disinformation and officially banned. The optimal solution turned out to be a six-cluster one (the method and distance measure were similar to those being used previously), and three types of users demonstrated the notable peripheral interest in «poisoned apples». The most curious thing was that greater interest in «VKontakte» and «Odnoklassniki» clearly coincided with certain versions of individualism and collectivism. This slightly reveals a huge hidden struggle front between «right» and «wrong» media literacy systems for assessing the veracity, and, respectively, between «right» and «wrong» people too.

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON STUDY METHOD IN EDUCATION

Toiymbaeva Zhanar Amantaevna

Teacher-researcher of the highest category, Teacher of Kazakh language and literature of the school-Lyceum "BINOM-" Tanym", Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan

Keywords: Lesson Study, effective, research, collective, scientific, influencing factor, joint plan, professional dialogue, collective culture, etc.

Abstract. The actual problem that I cover in this article is the use of Lesson Study, which is an action to improve the quality of students' knowledge and see its possible results. Lesson Study is an activity that gives a positive result in the learning process. In this work, subject teachers who teach the same class determine the level of knowledge of the student. Subject teachers make a joint plan. Therefore, the most powerful factor influencing a student's academic performance is the effective interaction of teachers. The joint activity of subject teachers develops teachers professionally, adapts them to find solutions to overcome emerging difficulties, and gives opportunity to achieve success and meet their goals.

I would like to focus on the effectiveness of the Lesson Study. First, this method forms and develops a professional dialogue between teachers. Second, it forms a collective culture. Third, teachers' attention is drawn to the educational needs of students. Fourth, it helps to have a deep understanding of the program, scientific concepts. Fifth, teachers develop professional pedagogical knowledge. Sixth, teachers develop lesson tracking and feedback skills. Seventh, teachers understand the scientific meaning of knowledge and become researchers. Eighth, the student's learning improves. Ninth, functional literacy develops. Finally, the person necessary for society is formed. Here is the effectiveness of this method.

Consequently, Lesson Study improves the lesson, increases the level of knowledge of the student, develops skills during the discussion of research stages, and exchanges new ideas.

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